

GUARDS Principles:

Findings from HDR UK Voices consultation

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Table of Contents

Introduction	3
Methods	3
Findings	8
Conclusions	19
Acknowledgements and further information	20
Appendix A: GUARDS Principles Survey	21
Appendix B: HDR UK Voices Newsletter	28

Introduction

This document reports the findings from a survey exploring [HDR UK Voices](#) members' perspectives on the draft version of the GUARDS¹ Principles. Developed by the [Pan UK Data Governance Steering Group](#) (the 'Steering Group'), part of the [UK Health Data Research Alliance](#), these principles serve as an overarching governance² framework for the data science community and are accompanied by detailed 'commitments' that outline effective implementation.

The GUARDS principles seek to address inefficiencies in research processes, reduce delays in vital research, promote public involvement, and encourage public trust. The draft version has undergone review in focused workshops with Steering Group members, including public representatives. Feedback from these workshops, along with insights gathered from this survey, will help refine the principles and commitments to ensure they are fit for purpose.

The ultimate goal is to create a benchmark for the data science community that promotes secure, transparent, and ethical data access within Secure Data Environments (SDEs)³ and beyond. This benchmark will respect and incorporate the public voice while demonstrating transparency in how data is used to advance research for public benefit.

Methods

From 17 June to 1 July 2024, we conducted a survey to collect feedback on the draft GUARDS principles inviting HDR UK Voices members to participate. Invitations were sent via newsletter on the survey's opening day (see Appendix A), and a reminder, including the survey deadline and reimbursement details, was sent on 10 July.

¹ Guided, Understandable, Aligned, Responsible, Delivers, and Stewardship

² The broad range of regulations, principles, and controls designed to ensure the safe, legal, and ethical use of data

³ Highly secure computing environment that provides researchers with remote access to data for approved research. SDEs are also known as Trusted Research Environments (TREs) or Data Safe Haven

The survey, hosted on SurveyMonkey, was refined with valuable feedback on its content, language, and accessibility from HDR UK [Public Advisory Board](#) members [Munisa Hashimi](#) and [Sara-Jane McAteer](#), who are also members of the Steering Group.

As part of the SurveyMonkey form, participants were provided with definitions of each principle and their commitments (see Table 1) and were asked to:

- Rate their agreement with the importance of the principle using a 5-point Likert-type scale, ranging from strong agreement to strong disagreement.
- Justify their responses, detailing how the principle resonated with them.
- Indicate whether the principle was easy to understand.
- Suggest changes or additions to the principle's definition.
- Assess if the commitments accurately reflected the principle.
- Propose changes to the listed commitments.

Appendix B contains all information and questions included in the SurveyMonkey form, which received 50 responses. In accordance with our [Honoraria and Expenses Policy](#), participants were reimbursed £25 each through a Love2Shop voucher.

Table 1. Principles and related commitments

Principle	Definition	Commitments
Guided	The design of data science infrastructure and its governance frameworks must be guided by a diverse range of public perspectives and be respectful of diverse viewpoints in developing core concepts and principles.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involving the public in developing governance processes for Secure Data Environments (SDEs), from formulating the underlying principles to implementing these processes and continuous improvement. • Involving the public in decision-making processes regarding data access.
Understandable	To build trust in data science and research data use, SDEs must be understandable to all stakeholders, with transparent mechanisms and decision-making processes and communications which are open, accessible, respectful, and considerate of diverse perspectives, identities, and backgrounds.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing and adopting an inclusive and shared language to explain research governance and safeguards, informed by public involvement. • Developing and adopting good practice standards for publicly accessible and transparent SDE operations. • Publishing stages, review criteria, and decision-making for data access in SDEs. • Providing easy-to-read materials in a variety of formats. • Maintaining accessible and complete data use registers
Aligned	Governance processes and accreditation standards should be aligned , robust, and auditable to avoid duplication of effort and cost.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aligning accreditation of SDEs to common standards and frameworks, metrics and reporting measures. • Adopting a common researcher registry for accreditation of users. • Following the Five Safes Framework with respect to managing research users and projects. • Adopting a standardised data access application form and contract templates. • Adopting a system of sharing data access decisions to promote consistency. • Following the FAIR guiding principles for data and metadata.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adopting a common definition and means of assessing what is meant by potential improvement to the public good.
Responsible	<p>The practice of population data science should be responsible, focusing on the public good, ensuring that research benefits are fairly distributed across society, and promoting fairness in data access for researchers.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring the processes and mechanisms for data access are fair, inclusive, and non-discriminatory for legitimate researchers from all backgrounds, strengthening capacity in under-represented groups. • Designing strategies for the data to be included in an SDE, along with the associated systems and processes, with a commitment to improving data equality and inclusivity and delivering fair outputs. • Empowering communities to shape and influence the use of their data for inclusive research. • Remaining open and respectful towards diverse global scientific approaches.
Delivers	<p>All use of public data should deliver public benefit. A standing infrastructure should be developed that is suited both to informing improvements to population health and wellbeing and to responding to emerging crises and needs. Research governance processes should be responsive to emerging challenges and contextual changes, balancing the robustness of safeguarding public rights with ensuring the potential of data is unlocked.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-developing tools with the public to understand what ‘public benefit’ means. • Conducting scenario testing to identify data needs under a range of plausible situations and how these relate to the needs of different population groups. • Adopting and testing strategies to improve research data processes, overcoming challenges to ensure progress and promoting continuous improvement. • Testing responsiveness to emerging challenges and changes in context involving the public
Stewardship	<p>Those implementing the data infrastructure and governance functions of population data science have</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agree and standardise training, career progression, and support to uphold professionalism in those with stewardship responsibilities.

a distinct set of **stewardship** responsibilities, and appropriate mechanisms are needed to support and nurture this community.

- Create distinct stewardship roles that are independent of those accessing or managing the data, with reporting pipelines and a remit to receive and respond to the public view.

Findings

Principle 1: Guided

The survey results indicated strong support for Principle 1 (see Table 1), with 76% of respondents strongly agreeing on its importance. An additional 16% agreed, while only a small minority expressed neutrality or disagreement. A detailed overview of responses can be found in Table 2.

Table 2. Level of agreement with the importance of Principle 1

Answer Choices	Responses	
Strongly agree	76.00%	38
Agree	16.00%	8
Neutral	2.00%	1
Disagree	4.00%	2
Strongly disagree	2.00%	1
	Answered	50
	Skipped	0

The qualitative feedback received highlights varied perspectives, with many underscoring the necessity of public participation to ensure research relevance, trust, and ethical considerations.

'I chose this response because I believe that the public have a right to understand what is being done with their data and diverse perspectives help to ensure that when that data is used to improve health outcomes, it has the capability to address health inequalities' – Survey respondent 22

'The public must be involved to ensure data collection and use is endorsed, understood, and trusted by them' – Survey respondent 47

Some respondents shared personal experiences or professional backgrounds to illustrate their points, while others emphasised the impact that participating in decision-making can have on them.

'I'm from a minority background and have experience of being on both sides of involvement/engagement - as a participant and an engagement lead. This principle ensures that labels like 'hard to reach' do not hinder contribution of diverse voices in the development of frameworks' – Survey respondent 13

'As the public are the ones whose data is being used it seems only fair that they have an involvement, and of course that needs to include diversity so that all sectors of the public are included. I have had the chance to be involved in the development of data use principles myself, as a PPI [Patient and Public Involvement] participant, and it has felt an empowering experience. It has also helped me feel more confident and positive about the idea of my data being used for research.' – Survey respondent 42

Additionally, 80% (40 out of 50 respondents) found the principle easy to understand, although a few suggested it could benefit from clearer wording and more specific guidelines.

'I found the first sentence difficult to process.' - Survey respondent 5

'It is a bit vague as to how exactly this will take place' - Survey respondent 1

'It could mean many things to many people' - Survey respondent 2

There was a general consensus (80%) that the listed commitments align with the principle, though some felt they lacked detail regarding diversity, missed safeguarding, and did not detail how public feedback should impact decision-making.

'It doesn't specify diversity' – Survey respondent 2

'Safeguarding is missing' – Survey respondent 7

'It's not clear whether the public should have an equal say in decision making. With the wording they could just be in an advisory role and their advice could be disregarded' – Survey respondent 5

Survey respondents also suggested improvements to the commitments, such as using simpler language, ensuring regular reviews with public involvement, and adding mechanisms for auditing progress and impact.

‘I would make the language simpler. At the moment they contain jargon and people will not understand them. They are not transparent’ – Survey respondent 3

‘Regular reviews with members of the public to ensure standards are continually met’ – Survey respondent 17

‘Audit progress/effectiveness with a member of the public in the team’ – Survey respondent 10

Principle 2: Understandable

The survey revealed a strong consensus on the importance of Principle 2 (see Table 1). A total of 82.98% of respondents strongly agreed with the principle, while 14.89% agreed. Notably, no respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed, indicating widespread support for this principle. Only 1 respondent remained neutral. A detailed overview of responses can be found in Table 3.

Table 3. Level of agreement with the importance of Principle 2

Answer Choices	Responses	
Strongly agree	82.98%	39
Agree	14.89%	7
Neutral	2.13%	1
Disagree	0.00%	0
Strongly disagree	0.00%	0
	Answered	47
	Skipped	3

However, survey participants emphasised the need for jargon-free, transparent, and ongoing communication to keep the public engaged.

'It's essential that the information is easy to understand and not jargon' – Survey respondent 21

'Transparency and ongoing communication are vital to prevent disengagement' – Survey respondent 6

While the principle was largely understood (76,6%, or 36 out of 47 respondents), some respondents found it abstract and suggested simplifying language and providing more concrete implementation steps.

'It makes sense but how exactly it will all happen is not obvious!' – Survey respondent 2

'I understand it, but if that were to be a lay definition, it's too long and wordy.' – Survey respondent 7

'Some concepts are a bit abstract.' – Survey respondent 10

Many proposed no changes to the current definition of commitments but emphasised the need for clearer guidance on how to align with this principle in practice, defined consequences for non-compliance, and accessible communication in various formats.

'A bit more information on what steps will be involved to achieve these principles' – Survey respondent 4

'I would include a consequence of failure to comply with easily understood information' – Survey respondent 16

'Including audio versions for better understanding for those with limitations such as eyesight/vision issues' – Survey respondent 31

Principle 3: Aligned

The survey results demonstrate strong support for Principle 3 (see Table 1), with 85.1% of respondents either strongly agreeing (53.19%) or agreeing (31.91%) on its importance. A smaller proportion of respondents were neutral, and only 1 disagreed. No respondents strongly disagreed. A detailed overview of responses can be found in Table 4.

Table 4. Level of agreement with the importance of Principle 3

Answer Choices	Responses	
Strongly agree	53.19%	25
Agree	31.91%	15
Neutral	12.77%	6
Disagree	2.13%	1
Strongly disagree	0.00%	0
	Answered	47
	Skipped	3

The reasons for the agreement varied, including cost-efficiency, public assurance, and alignment with industry standards. However, some felt that the principle was complicated and challenging to achieve.

'I agree that the processes should be robust and easy to analyse and agree that this is really important to avoid additional costs.' – Survey respondent 1

'Many people have significant concerns about usage and storage of data; this principle and commitments' provide reassurance' – Survey respondent 6

'Harmonisation ensures that the same approach is industry wide'- Survey respondent 15

'Sounds complicated and hard to achieve' – Survey respondent 36

While 48.94% of respondents (23 out of 47) found the principle easy to understand, some felt it was not (17.02%, or 8 out of 47) or were unsure (34.04%, or 16 out of 47), citing jargon and complexity as barriers.

'Again, easy for professionals to understand but requires plain English for public' – Survey respondent 4

'These are complex ideas and grasping them requires a frame of mind.' – Survey respondent 10

Suggestions for improvement included simplifying the language, providing clearer explanations, and clarifying its applicability to the private sector.

‘Shorten the sentences, easier to understand’ – Survey respondent 4

‘[The] Statement could be a bit more explanatory especially for the lay person it should be easier to understand.’ – Survey respondent 1

‘Public v private sector is the process identical? Are there greater safeguards needed in private sector [?]’ – Survey respondent 39

Despite these concerns, 78.72% of respondents (37 out of 47) felt that the commitments reflected the principle, although some noted the absence of monitoring accreditation and the need for greater emphasis on involvement and inclusion.

‘I would add alignment with the "Include Framework" and "Involve Framework" to establish benchmark standards aligned with good practice in Data Research Inclusion and Involvement practices’ – Survey respondent 18

‘There is no mention of who will monitor the accreditation.’ – Survey respondent 20

Principle 4: Responsible

The survey results highlight support for Principle 4 (see Table 1), with 69.57% of respondents strongly agreeing and an additional 28.26% agreeing on its importance. Only 1 respondent remained neutral, and no one expressed disagreement or strong disagreement. A detailed overview of response can be found in Table 5.

Table 5. Level of agreement with the importance of Principle 4

Answer Choices	Responses	
Strongly agree	69.57%	32
Agree	28.26%	12
Neutral	2.17%	1
Disagree	0.00%	0

Strongly disagree	0.00%	0
	Answered	46
	Skipped	4

According to some, the principle resonated with them because it emphasises the involvement of diverse backgrounds, which is considered crucial for achieving high-quality results and increasing participant engagement.

‘You will always get the highest quality of results if people from a broad diverse background are involved. Encouragement for further participation will also increase when participants are provided the findings, given advice on how successful it was and opportunities to remain involved.’ – Survey respondent 1

There was also recognition that the responsible use of data is vital for maintaining trust and achieving public benefit. However, some respondents found the language complex and suggested simplifying the text for clarity.

‘Responsible use of health data, for purposes as stated and requested is vital to build trust among all parties involved and for that professional relationship to be sustained’ – Survey respondent 1

‘The principles are important but the sentences are complex and would be better shortened or linked when there is commonality’ – Survey respondent 4

Despite these remarks, 80.43% of respondents (37 out of 46) found the principle easy to understand, while a few (17.39%, or 8 out of 46) remained unsure due to the complexity of the task and the potential for varied interpretations.

‘It’s complex. People will debate endlessly about this.’ – Survey respondent 6

‘Could mean many things to many people’ – Survey respondent 4

Most felt the commitments align with the principle (80.43%, or 37 out of 46 respondents), but some called for more specific examples and for addressing complex issues such as privacy and detection of fraud.

‘Details of how they would be achieved’ – Survey respondent 7

‘I suggest to add/ amending the commitment along these lines: that it enhances privacy protection and fraud detection.’ – Survey respondent 28

Principle 5: Delivers

The survey results indicated strong support for Principle 5 (see Table 1), with 65.22% of respondents strongly agreeing and an additional 28.26% agreeing on its importance. A small minority remained neutral, while no respondents expressed disagreement or strong disagreement. A detailed overview of responses can be found in Table 6.

Table 6. Level of agreement with the importance of Principle 5

Answer Choices	Responses	
Strongly agree	65.22%	30
Agree	28.26%	13
Neutral	6.52%	3
Disagree	0.00%	0
Strongly disagree	0.00%	0
	Answered	46
	Skipped	4

The significance of this principle was largely attributed to its potential for delivering tangible public benefits and encouraging future involvement in studies. However, some concerns were raised about the clarity of language, the practicality of its implementation, and the challenge of balancing benefits with commercial interests.

'Delivering tangible public benefit will encourage and increase involvement in future studies. It resonates well as it has increased my involvement in previous studies.' – Survey respondent 1

'The language used is hard.' – Survey respondent 3

'It's very high level so it would be hard to test and reject a proposal on the grounds that it doesn't comply' – Survey respondent 5

'Concern at the question of 'balancing' safeguarding and potential in the context of commercial activity.' – Survey respondent 6

A few respondents suggested that the principle should be more specific, particularly in defining public benefit and the elements of scenario testing. Additionally, some recommended incorporating more flexibility and a stronger emphasis on safeguarding public rights.

'More specific - what do you mean by public benefit? which public?' – Survey respondent 10

'Explain how these scenario testing is developed and what is meant by plausible situations' – Survey respondent 30

'The first sentence should be extended with the addition of the words 'while safeguarding public rights' – Survey respondent 6

80.43% of respondents (37 out of 46) felt that the listed commitments reflect the principle adequately. However, several suggested improvements, including setting clearer expectations and providing more details about how and when these commitments will take place in practice, potentially referencing relevant case studies.

'Overcoming challenges is quite a broad statement and could unfairly set expectations' – Survey respondent 1

'Details of HOW' – Survey respondent 7

‘Just to include the time scale of this. So the public can see the commitments’ – Survey respondent 40

‘Add some case study’ – Survey respondent 32

Principle 6: Stewardship

The results show strong support for Principle 6 (see Table 1), with 69.57% of participants strongly agreeing and 19.57% agreeing on its importance. A small proportion of respondents were neutral or disagreed, and none strongly disagreed. A detailed overview of responses can be found in Table 7.

Table 7. Level of agreement with the importance of Principle 6

Answer Choices	Responses	
Strongly agree	69.57%	32
Agree	19.57%	9
Neutral	6.52%	3
Disagree	4.35%	2
Strongly disagree	0.00%	0
	Answered	46
	Skipped	4

Respondents noted that independent stewardship is crucial for maintaining the credibility and effectiveness of data governance processes, ensuring accountability, and fostering trust with patients, their families, and the general public.

‘Independent stewardship is very important to enforce and maintain credibility of the process. Stewards must also be motivated and feel included or quality and effort may drop off.’ – Survey respondent 1

‘Without a designated person, or small group of people, taking ownership and acting as a bridge between patient and researcher group, it would be nigh on impossible to move things forward effectively.’ – Survey respondent 7

'Good [...] governance is not only expected but is needed where patients' data is being used on mass. It is vital to build and maintain trust with the public/patients and their families.' – Survey respondent 27

Despite widespread agreement on the importance of this principle, some found the term 'stewardship' ambiguous and suggested offering more detailed explanations of how stewardship will be implemented, funded, and assessed.

'It's unclear what is meant by stewardship it's not a commonly known term.' – Survey respondent 16

'Much more detail about what stewardship means in this context and how it will be actioned.' – Survey respondent 7

'Clarity about how this will be funded in the long term.' – Survey respondent 24

'How are stewardship roles monitored?' – Survey respondent 30

Additionally, there were calls for clarification on how stewardship connects to public involvement in governance and suggested that professionals should be trained not only in data delivery but also in understanding its impact on public benefit.

'It needs to clarify how stewardship relates to the public being involved in governance.' – Survey respondent 8

'I think that professionals should be trained not just in data delivery but also in all it is necessary for the public benefit, in particular for patients and carers.' – Survey respondent 41

The majority of respondents (76.09%, or 35 out of 46) felt the commitments reflected the principle, while 10.87% (or 5 out of 46) disagreed, and 13.04% (or 6 out of 46) were unsure. The suggestions for improvement included clearer language, more concrete actions (e.g., sanctions for breaches, oversight of stewardship, and a clearer definition of stewardship roles), and stronger public involvement in decision-making.

'Make the sentences less complex.' – Survey respondent 4

'See above for breaches of the commitments [...] need a system of enforceable sanctions otherwise the Principles are worthless.' – Survey respondent 9

'I would include the word oversight not just reporting responsibilities.' – Survey respondent 17

'The role of the Stewardship needs to be clearly defined' – Survey respondent 40

'I would like to see more about who would be undertaking the stewardship and that it would include direct public representation as well as seeking views of the public.' – Survey respondent 6

Additional comments

The additional comments received from 39 survey respondents on the GUARDS principles reflected many of the areas for improvement already discussed. Survey respondents appreciated the clarity and care in defining the principles but noted that simplifying the language would improve accessibility and understanding. Concerns were raised about the lack of detailed implementation strategies and enforceable measures, with calls for including practical examples, clearer pathways for raising concerns, and actions to address minority group representation. Further suggestions included providing a draft for feedback, incorporating a glossary of terms, and adapting the principles to different scenarios. Some feedback also pointed to issues with the length of the survey, suggesting reducing content in the future to encourage participation.

Conclusions

The findings from this survey indicate strong support from HDR UK Voices members for the draft GUARDS Principles, underscoring their importance in promoting transparency, inclusivity, and trust in data governance within the research community. Overall, participants expressed clear support for principles that emphasise public involvement, ethical use of data, and accountability, while also identifying areas for improvement, particularly regarding clarity of language and practical implementation. The feedback received will be instrumental in refining the principles and

commitments to ensure they align with public expectations and can be effectively applied in SDEs. As these principles evolve, they must remain accessible, adaptable, and responsive to the diverse perspectives of the public, ultimately encouraging a research environment that is both transparent and accountable to those whose data is being used.

Acknowledgements and further information

We would like to thank everyone who participated in the survey and contributed to the development of the GUARDS Principles. The valuable feedback received, along with input from other stakeholders, will inform the final version.

Our gratitude also goes to Tara Dowd, former HDR UK Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) Officer, for her efforts in facilitating the reimbursement of participants and managing inquiries received via email.

Special thanks to Bethany Gilbert, HDR UK Research and Governance Project Officer, for organising the survey responses received, whose insights were presented in the findings section.

If you have any questions or need further clarification about this work or the report, please contact the HDR UK PPIE team at involvement@hdrug.ac.uk.

Appendix A: GUARDS Principles Survey

PAGE 1 - Welcome to the GUARDS Principles Survey

Thank you for choosing to participate in this survey! Your views are really important for the development of this work. We value your honesty, so please don't feel pressured to craft perfect sentences. Before you begin, we want to inform you that by taking part, you agree to the use of your answers in an anonymous format for various purposes (e.g., reports, posters, journal articles, blogs, or content shared across HDR UK's social media channels and webpages). Also, rest assured that any details that could potentially identify you as an individual will not be shared in any published materials. If you have any questions or require this survey in a different format, please get in touch with the Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement team at involvement@hdruk.ac.uk.

PAGE 2 - GUARDS Principles Survey: Focus

This survey is seeking public involvement to inform the work of the [Pan UK Data Governance Steering Group](#), part of the [UK Health Data Research Alliance](#). The Steering Group is developing a set of overarching governance principles for population data science, where data is accessed in Secure Data Environments, also known as [Trusted Research Environments](#). The aim of the principles is to create a unifying framework for all parties involved in data access. This will ensure all parties adhere to strong data governance standards and include meaningful public involvement, contributing to addressing inefficiencies in research processes, delays in vital research, and lack of public trust. These principles will have wide-reaching applications across UK nations and disciplines where health, socioeconomic, and environmental data are accessed and linked for research purposes.

Glossary of terms:

Research/data governance: the broad range of regulations, principles, and controls designed to ensure the safe, legal, and ethical use of data.

Secure Data Environment (SDE): the highly secure computing environment that provides remote access to data for approved research. It allows researchers to access data from a single, secure

location, ensuring that no personal data ever leaves the SDE. SDEs are also known as Trusted Research Environments (TREs) or Data Safe Haven.

PAGE 3 - **GUARDS Principles Survey: Disclosure**

The principles included in this survey are very much a work in progress, and your views are crucial to shaping them in a way that is accessible and relevant to the public. We acknowledge the technicalities and specificities of the topic and have done our best to make it accessible, with feedback from Public Advisory Board members included in the [Pan UK Data Governance Steering Group](#). However, as they have mentioned, there is still a lot of work to be done, and we need more public help. We aim to use the feedback received through this survey to inform changes and develop a version ready for further consultations with the public in a different format (e.g., workshops).

GUARDS Principles Survey: Instructions

This survey seeks your views on the draft version of the **GUARDS** principles. The acronym GUARDS stand for:

- **G**uided
- **U**nderstandable
- **A**ligned
- **R**esponsible
- **D**elivers
- **S**tewardship

On the following pages of the survey, each principle is explained with a definition and examples of the context in which they will apply, framed as ‘commitments’ for the data science community. For each principle, you will be asked six questions to help us understand your opinions on their relevance, acceptability, and accessibility.

Thank you for participating in the first round of public consultations on the GUARDS principles. We deeply appreciate your help and time!

PAGE 4 - Principle 1: Guided

Definition of the principle:

The design of data science infrastructure and its governance frameworks must be **guided** by a diverse range of public perspectives and be respectful of diverse viewpoints in developing core concepts and principles.

Following this principle means making these commitments:

- Involving the public in developing governance processes for Secure Data Environments, from formulating the underlying principles to implementing these processes and continuous improvement.
- Involving the public in decision-making processes regarding data access.

1. Please indicate your level of agreement with the importance of this principle for data science.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

2. Why did you choose this response? How did this principle resonate with you, if at all?

3. Is the principle easy to understand?

- Yes
- No
- I am not sure (please specify)

4. What would you change or add to the current definition of the principle?

5. Do you feel the commitments listed reflect the principle?

- Yes
- No

- I am not sure (please specify)

6. What would you change or add to the commitment(s)?

PAGE 5 - Principle 2: Understandable

Definition of the principle:

To build trust in data science and research data use, Secure Data Environments (SDEs) must be **understandable** to all stakeholders, with transparent mechanisms and decision-making processes and communications which are open, accessible, respectful, and considerate of diverse perspectives, identities, and backgrounds.

Following this principle means making these commitments:

- Developing and adopting an inclusive and shared language to explain research governance and safeguards, informed by public involvement.
- Developing and adopting good practice standards for publicly accessible and transparent SDE operations.
- Publishing stages, review criteria, and decision-making for data access in SDEs.
- Providing easy-to-read materials in a variety of formats.
- Maintaining accessible and complete data use registers

*Six questions as per pp.24-25.

PAGE 6 - Principle 3: Aligned

Definition of the principle:

Governance processes and accreditation standards should be **aligned**, robust, and auditable to avoid duplication of effort and cost.

Following this principle means making these commitments:

- Aligning accreditation of Secure Data Environments to common standards and frameworks, metrics and reporting measures.

- Adopting a common researcher registry for accreditation of users.
- Following the [Five Safes Framework](#) with respect to managing research users and projects.
- Adopting a standardised data access application form and contract templates.
- Adopting a system of sharing data access decisions to promote consistency.
- Following the FAIR guiding principles for data and metadata.
- Adopting a common definition and means of assessing what is meant by potential improvement to the public good.

*Six questions as per pp.24-25.

PAGE 7 - Principle 4: Responsible

Definition of the principle:

The practice of population data science should be **responsible**, focusing on the public good, ensuring that research benefits are fairly distributed across society, and promoting fairness in data access for researchers.

Following this principle means making these commitments:

- Ensuring the processes and mechanisms for data access are fair, inclusive, and non-discriminatory for legitimate researchers from all backgrounds, strengthening capacity in under-represented groups.
- Designing strategies for the data to be included in a Secure Data Environment, along with the associated systems and processes, with a commitment to improving data equality and inclusivity and delivering fair outputs.
- Empowering communities to shape and influence the use of their data for inclusive research.
- Remaining open and respectful towards diverse global scientific approaches.

*Six questions as per pp.24-25.

PAGE 8 - Principle 5: Delivers

Definition of the principle:

All use of public data should **deliver** public benefit. A standing infrastructure should be developed that is suited both to informing improvements to population health and wellbeing and to responding to emerging crises and needs. Research governance processes should be responsive to emerging challenges and contextual changes, balancing the robustness of safeguarding public rights with ensuring the potential of data is unlocked.

Following this principle means making these commitments:

- Co-developing tools with the public to understand what ‘public benefit’ means.
- Conducting scenario testing to identify data needs under a range of plausible situations and how these relate to the needs of different population groups.
- Adopting and testing strategies to improve research data processes, overcoming challenges to ensure progress and promoting continuous improvement.
- Testing responsiveness to emerging challenges and changes in context involving the public.

*Six questions as per pp.24-25.

PAGE 9 - Principle 6: Stewardship

Definition of the principle:

Those implementing the data infrastructure and governance functions of population data science have a distinct set of **stewardship** responsibilities, and appropriate mechanisms are needed to support and nurture this community.

Following this principle means making these commitments:

- Agree and standardise training, career progression, and support to uphold professionalism in those with stewardship responsibilities.
- Create distinct stewardship roles that are independent of those accessing or managing the data, with reporting pipelines and a remit to receive and respond to the public view.

*Six questions as per pp.24-25.

PAGE 10 - Additional comments

Do you have any additional comments regarding the **GUARDS** (Guided, Understandable, Aligned, Responsible, Delivers, and Stewardship) principles and their commitments? Is there anything we have missed?

PAGE 11 - Survey Complete

Thank you so much for your contribution! Your input is incredibly valuable to us. Please don't forget to add your email address below so the Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement team can send you the Love2Shop e-Gift Card. Rest assured, your email address will only be used for this purpose, and your information will be processed according to [HDR UK's Privacy Policy](#).

Email address

Appendix B: HDR UK Voices Newsletter

HDR UK Voices

Hello HDR UK Voices member,

We hope you had a lovely weekend!

We are reaching out to share an exciting opportunity to engage with the [Pan-UK Data Governance Steering Group](#).

The Pan-UK Data Governance Steering Group is a working group of the [UK Health Data Research Alliance](#), bringing together data custodians and policymakers from across the UK's four nations. Their current focus is on developing a set of overarching governance principles for population data science, where data is accessed in Secure Data Environments – also known as [Trusted Research Environments](#). These principles will have wide-reaching applications across UK nations and disciplines where health, socioeconomic, and environmental data are accessed and linked for research purposes.

Your input matters!

To ensure these principles are clear, relevant and widely accepted, the Pan UK Data Governance Steering Group need your input! If you are a UK resident aged 18 or over, we invite you to contribute to this important effort.

How you can get involved

Click the blue tab below to access the survey, review the principles, and provide your insights. The survey will take approximately 30 to 40 minutes to complete and **will close on Monday, 01 July, at 23:59 BST**. As a token of appreciation for your contribution, you will receive a £25 Love2Shop e-Gift Card via email within two weeks from the deadline date.

Survey

If you have any questions or require this survey in a different format, please reach out to our Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement team at involvement@hdruk.ac.uk. They will be happy to help!

If you would like to learn more about the work we do at HDR UK, please visit our website at <https://www.hdruk.ac.uk/>.

Best wishes,
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